

1

tokk'aano

2

hoolgok

3

yok'enodzeedz

4

hen

5

hoolyo

6

tookk'e

2

landslide

1

erosion

4

river

3

drone
**“bumblebee in
the sky”**

6

fish

5

weather

7

le'on

8

maahaa hots'edelyaaye

9

taa'gettletl

10

taats

11

too

12

daas

8

subsistence

7

**rock,
boulder**

10

sand

9

fishing

12

sandbar

11

water